

A Guided Tour of Electron Transfer Reactions[†]

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The author's research work focuses attention on the kinetics of electron transfer reactions, with particular reference to the oxidation of organic and inorganic substrates by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III). This kinetic investigation has been an attempt to extend the scope of this extremely efficient and versatile one-electron oxidant, in acid and alkaline media, and to explore and establish mechanistic pathways of diverse kinds of reactions.

METAL ion oxidants can function either as one-equivalent or two-equivalent reagents. One-equivalent oxidants are those which accept a single electron by direct transfer or by interaction with a hydrogen atom. In one-equivalent redox processes, the change of valency can be brought about by either an inner-sphere or an outer-sphere mechanism. In an outer sphere mechanism, the inner coordination shell of both reagents is preserved intact in the transition state. Since the metal-ligand distances will be affected by valency changes, some distortion of the inner shells would occur, but no metal-ligand bond would be broken or formed.

Most organic reaction processes are explicable in terms of electron shifts accompanying bond formation and bond breaking. The rates and activation energies of such reactions are therefore of considerable interest. In the reactions of one-equivalent oxidants with organic substrates, the most frequently encountered oxidation process would seem to correspond to an electron transfer between substrate and oxidant, accompanied by the breaking of a C-H bond and loss of proton to give a substrate radical, as for example¹,

It would be expected that the loss of a proton would be slower than electron transfer, and hence would correspond to the rate-determining step.

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, is a substitution-inert transition metal complex². It does not exchange its ligands at a rate fast enough to compete with rapid electron transfer. The mechanism of oxidation by hexacyanoferrate(III) is via an outer sphere process, the transfer of an electron occurring from the substrate to the metal ion through the cyano ligand. There exists the distinct possibility of the formation of radical intermediates, as a result of abstraction of an electron, by the hexacyanoferrate(III), from the substrate.

The present paper highlights the work carried out in this laboratory pertaining to the versatile

nature of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) as an oxidising agent capable of effecting diverse kinds of reactions.

The reactions were followed by observing the disappearance of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ at 420 nm spectrophotometrically. All reactions were performed under a nitrogen atmosphere.

Oxidation of aromatic hydrocarbons

The kinetics of oxidation of toluenes by hexacyanoferrate(III) were studied in acetic acid-water mixtures at varying acidities of perchloric acid. The reactions showed a first order dependence on each of the reactants (substrate, oxidant and acid). The first order dependence of the reaction rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ indicated that the reactive oxidant species was the protonated form, $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$. A spectral shift in the absorption maximum from 420 to 435 nm confirmed the formation of $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$. Increasing proportions of acetic acid had resulted in an increase in the rate of the reaction, suggesting an ion-dipole type of interaction. The role of the solvent could be rationalised on the basis of factors such as the dielectric constant, acidity of the medium, the solvating power of the solvent, solvent structure and solute-solvent interactions.

The kinetic rates of oxidation were in accordance with the theory of electronic substituent effects. It was observed that electron-releasing groups caused an acceleration in the rate, while electron-withdrawing groups caused a retardation. Plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ against σ^+ gave values of $\rho^+ = -0.90, -1.8, -1.3$ and -0.5 for xylenes, halotoluenes, nitrotoluenes and methoxytoluenes³, respectively, which were in the range for processes involving the formation of radical intermediates in the rate-determining step⁴.

Kinetic isotope effects gave $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$ values of 6.0, 6.0, 6.2 and 6.0 for xylenes, halotoluenes, nitrotoluenes and methoxytoluenes, respectively, indicating that the rate-determining step involved the cleavage of the carbon-hydrogen bond of the methyl group attached to the aryl ring, resulting in the formation

[†]Rev. Fr. L. M. Yeddapanalli Memorial Lecture (1987) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on December 26, 1986 at Calcutta.

of a radical intermediate⁸. In the oxidation of some organic substrates, similar k_H/k_D values had indicated cleavage of the C-H bond giving a radical⁸. Further a less polar transition state would also contribute to the formation of a radical intermediate rather than an ionic species, in the rate-determining step of the reaction. This was supported by the observed increase in the rate of the reaction, with a decrease in the polarity of the solvent medium.

Iron(III) is known to be an effective oxidiser of radical species⁹ and could combine with the radical to yield a stable carbocation (R^+) according to the reaction, $R \cdot + Fe^{3+} \longrightarrow R^+ + Fe^{2+}$. This carbocation would presumably be formed in a fast step, and no evidence could be obtained for its formation either from the Hammett plot or from the kinetic isotope effect, both of which indicated a radical intermediate in the rate-determining step of the reaction. Moreover, the radical underwent rapid conversion, in a series of steps, to give the product (the corresponding aldehyde).

The sequence of reactions is shown in Scheme 1,

Scheme 1.

Oxidation of arylalkanes

The kinetics of oxidation of aryl alkanes (diphenylmethane, triphenylmethane and fluorene) by acidic hexacyanoferrate(III) showed a first order dependence on each, substrate and oxidant, but was observed to be independent of the concentration of acid in the range studied. The absence of a spectral shift in the absorption maximum from 420 nm, indicated that the reactive oxidant species was the $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ ion.

The reaction was susceptible to changes in the polarity of the solvent medium. In going from 80 to 95% acetic acid, the polarity decreases, which causes an increase in the rate of the reaction. Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ against the reciprocal of dielectric constant were linear, indicating that the reaction was of the ion-dipole type. It might also be argued that an inhibition of the rate of the reaction by water could be caused by a reduction in the acidity of the medium. Linear plots of $\log k_{obs}$ against H_0 (extrapolated from Wiberg's data¹⁰) gave slopes of 0.7 and 0.4 for diphenylmethane and triphenylmethane, respectively, from 80 to 95% acetic acid

($HClO_4 = 0.01 M$). This would indicate that a correlation of the rate with H_0 (when the solvent composition was varied at constant acid concentration) cannot be completely ruled out. Moreover, the transition state is less polar than the initial state (reactants), because of the increased dispersal of charge in the transition state. The decrease in the rate of oxidation, on the addition of a more polar solvent, is a natural consequence of the progressive increase in solvation of the reactants more than that in the transition state. The effect of a change in solvent composition on reaction rates would also depend on factors such as solvent structure and solute-solvent interactions.

Conjugation influences and resonance factors seem to play a prominent role in these reactions. In this series, fluorene was oxidised fastest, since the 9-position of the fluorene molecule was particularly labile. The greater oxidation rate of fluorene over diphenylmethane and triphenylmethane may be due to the electromeric effect, which would be expected to be higher in fluorene. Steric hindrance due to the triarylmethane group would result in triphenylmethane being oxidised at a faster rate compared to diphenylmethane. In the case of fluorene, the introduction of electron-releasing groups caused an increase in the rate, whereas electron-withdrawing groups caused a decrease in the rate of the reaction. A plot of $\log k_{obs}$ against σ^+ gave a value of $\sigma^+ = -1.5$, indicating that the initial reaction was the abstraction of a hydrogen atom, forming a radical intermediate in the rate-determining step of the reaction. Earlier investigations had shown that hydrogen atom abstractions from toluene, yielding a radical⁸, gave values of ρ between -0.75 and -1.5. Chromic acid oxidation of diphenylmethane¹¹ had yielded ρ values of -1.40, demonstrating the formation of radical intermediates.

When the reaction was carried out using 9,9-dideuteriofluorene, the rate of the reaction was decreased by a factor of 6.0, which indicated the cleavage of the carbon-hydrogen bond in the rate-determining step of the reaction, resulting in the formation of a radical intermediate. The chromic acid oxidation of diphenylmethane had demonstrated a k_H/k_D value of 6.4, wherein the rate-determining step had been established as the cleavage of the methylene carbon-hydrogen bond, forming a benzhydryl radical¹². Radical formation has been confirmed by esr spectroscopy. Further evidence in support of the radical mechanism may be found in a comparison of the rates of hydrogen abstraction from toluene, diphenylmethane, triphenylmethane and fluorene, and the rates of solvolysis of the corresponding chlorides (Table 1). The relative rates of oxidation of these substrates were observed to be 1 : 12 : 22 : 230, which appeared to be too small to be attributed to an ionic pathway. There was areement between the relative rates of oxidation and the rates of hydrogen atom

removal, but the range of rates of solvolysis was much larger.

TABLE 1—RELATIVE RATES OF OXIDATION, HYDROGEN ABSTRACTION AND SOLVOLYSIS

Substrate	Relative rate of oxidation	Relative rate of hydrogen abstraction by $\cdot\text{OCl}_2^a$	Relative rate of solvolysis of chlorides ^b
Toluene	1.0	1.0	1.0
Diphenylmethane	12.0	8.0	2.0×10^3
Triphenylmethane	22.0	16.7	1.0×10^7

^aE. C. KOOYMAN, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1950, 6^o, 492.

^bA. STRITWITSCHER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1956, 56, 571.

In the oxidations of these substrates, the rate-determining step was the abstraction of a hydrogen atom, giving a radical⁶. The subsequent conversion of the radical to the product, in all cases, was rapid. The trend of observed reactivity (fluorene > triphenylmethane > diphenylmethane) is justifiable on the basis of the stability of the products. In the case of fluorene and diphenylmethane, the products obtained were ketones, which could be stabilised by conjugation influences more than the parent hydrocarbons. In the case of triphenylmethane, the presence of three bulky groups would facilitate the formation of the triphenylmethyl radical. The product, triphenylcarbinol, would be formed quite easily, even though this product would not have any carbonyl stabilisation with the pi-bonded aromatic system. This would account for the faster rate of oxidation for triphenylmethane over that for diphenylmethane.

Oxidative cleavage of unsaturated compounds

The carbon-carbon double bond in unsaturated compounds is quite reactive, and there exists the distinct possibility of the abstraction of an electron by hexacyanoferrate(II), in acid medium, from the carbon-carbon double bond of these unsaturated compounds, leading to the oxidative cleavage of the double bond to yield aldehydes.

In the present investigation, the unsaturated compounds used included styrene, crotonic acid and cinnamic acid. These substrates have been oxidised by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in acid medium, using aqueous acetic acid as solvent, under a nitrogen atmosphere.

The rate of the reaction depends on the first powers of the concentrations of the reactants (substrate, oxidant and acid). The observed dependence of the rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ suggests that the first step is the protonation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$ to give $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$. The rate-determining step of the reaction is the abstraction of an electron by $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$ from the carbon-carbon double bond of the substrate, to give a cationic intermediate. The ρ^+ values of -4.2 (for styrenes) and -4.0 (for cinnamic acids) support the formation of a cationic

intermediate in the rate-determining step of the reaction. Earlier studies involving the bromination of styrenes, had reported values of $\rho = -4.01$, indicating a fully developed benzylic carbonium ion-like transition state in the slow step of the reaction⁹.

The oxidation of α -deuteriostyrene (1) gave a negligible secondary deuterium kinetic isotope effect, $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.98$, while the oxidation of β - β -dideuteriostyrene (2) gave an inverse secondary deuterium kinetic isotope effect, $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.80$.

For the oxidation of 1, $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.98$ is reasonable since the α -carbon, in going from an olefinic centre to a carbonium ion-like character during the process of electron abstraction by $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$, would remain sp^2 in character. For the oxidation of 2, $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.80$; this would indicate a change in the state of hybridisation from sp^2 to sp^3 for the terminal carbon atom (β -carbon). Since the oxidation of styrene exhibited an inverse secondary deuterium isotope effect only at the β -carbon, this would suggest that the rate-determining step of the reaction produced a carbonium ion in which the α -carbon remained sp^2 in character. In the case of deuterated cinnamic acids, the rate of the reaction showed an inverse kinetic isotope effect when either the α or β proton was replaced by deuterium ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.83$). The formation of a cationic intermediate is supported by the inverse kinetic isotope effect, $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.83$. This suggests that in going from the ground state to the transition state, one or more carbon atoms undergo a change from the sp^2 to the sp^3 state¹⁰.

In this investigation, experimental evidence supports a mechanism wherein the rate-determining step involved electron abstraction from the carbon-carbon double bond of the substrate by $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$, to give a cationic intermediate. The subsequent steps were rapid, yielding aldehydes as the major products. Earlier reports have established that the cleavage of 1,2-glycols gave aldehydes as the major products^{11,12}. The formation of these products substantiated the proposed mechanism of the oxidation process, wherein there was a cleavage of the carbon-carbon bond in the final step of the reaction¹³.

Oxidation of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons

The oxidation of naphthalene by various oxidants usually yields either naphthoquinone or phthalic acid as the product^{14,15}, while the oxidation of phenanthrene usually gives either phenanthroquinone or phenanthroic acid as the product¹⁶. However, the present kinetic investigation on the oxidation of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons

(naphthalene and phenanthrene) by acidic hexacyanoferrate(III), have yielded unusual products. For example, the oxidation of naphthalene had yielded α -naphthol in approximately 35–45% conversion¹⁷, while the oxidation of phenanthrene yielded 9-hydroxyphenanthrene in approximately 25–30% conversion¹⁸. The other products were the starting materials (naphthalene and phenanthrene, respectively), indicating that the actual yields of the products were higher than the percent of conversion, in both cases.

The rate of the reaction was dependent on the concentrations of each of the reactants (substrate, oxidant and acid). The first step of the reaction was the protonation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ to give $\text{HFe}(\text{CN})_6^{2-}$. This oxidant species reacts with the substrate to give an aromatic cation radical. The lack of any primary deuterium isotope effect ($k_H/k_D=0.6$), when the reaction was performed with naphthalene- d_8 , indicated that there was no cleavage of the carbon-hydrogen bonds in the transition state. The Hammett plot yielded a value of $\rho=-4.0$ (corr. coeff.=0.99) for naphthalenes and phenanthrenes, suggesting the formation of an aromatic radical cation in the rate-determining step of the reaction.

During the course of the reaction there was no rupture of the aromatic ring. This was confirmed by the nature of the products formed (α -naphthol from naphthalene; 9-hydroxyphenanthrene from phenanthrene) by the oxidation of these polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons by acidic hexacyanoferrate(III) using 90% aqueous acetic acid as solvent, under a nitrogen atmosphere.

Oxidative coupling of phenols and aromatic amines

Phenols :

The chemical oxidation of phenols is complex, in that (i) it usually gives a mixture of products, and (ii) with the same phenol, different oxidants can yield quite different product mixtures.

In the presence of oxidising agents, phenolic molecules can undergo either carbon-carbon or carbon-oxygen coupling to give a variety of products. Simple phenols can be linked at positions *ortho* and/or *para* to the hydroxyl group to yield several possible dimers; these can be further oxidised to produce trimers, polymers and quinonoid-type structures. In more complex polyhydroxy-aromatic compounds, coupling of both types may occur-intramolecular as well as intermolecular coupling. Substitution products and compounds resulting from coupling at benzylic positions may also be observed.

The oxidation of phenols by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium would give the aryloxy anion. This anion can transfer an electron to hexacyanoferrate(III), resulting in the formation of an aryloxy radical. The radical would then be free to react, and the formation of coupled products is a distinct possibility.

In the present investigation, the phenols chosen for purposes of oxidation by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), in alkaline medium, in aqueous methanol solvent, at constant ionic strength, under a nitrogen atmosphere, have included monohydric, dihydric, trihydric and polynuclear phenols. The rates of the reactions were dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of substrate, oxidant and alkali. Variations in the ionic strength of the media and the addition of hexacyanoferrate(II) ions, did not have any effect on the rates of the reactions.

Pummerer *et al.*^{19,20} postulated a free phenoxy radical as the first intermediate in the oxidation of phenols. In the present study, the radical intermediates formed have been characterised by esr spectroscopy. The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of resorcinol, exhibited 12 spectral lines. A large triplet splitting was observed, arising from the equivalent protons at positions 4 and 6. The remaining two doublet splittings would correspond to protons at positions 2 and 5. The esr spectrum of the radical, obtained from the oxidation of pyrogallol, gave two groups of 3 lines each resulting from hyperfine interactions of protons on the ring with the unpaired electron spin. The resonance forms of this semiquinone structure would make protons at positions 4 and 6 equivalent. The observed splitting of the line follows from doubling due to the proton at position 5, followed by tripling of each of these two lines by the remaining equivalent protons at positions 4 and 6. The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of phloroglucinol, exhibited a 1 : 3 : 3 : 1 quartet, due to the 3 equivalent protons at positions 2, 4 and 6.

The alkali dependence of the oxidation process indicated that these reactions proceeded via the intermediate anion of the reducing substrate formed with the hydroxyl ions. The phenol coupling mechanism can be best explained by visualising that the anions formed were oxidised by hexacyanoferrate(III) in slow steps to give the radical species, which have been detected by esr spectroscopy. The radicals then undergo rapid and irreversible coupling to yield the products. The reaction sequence is shown in Scheme 2. Analytical and spectral methods have been used for the characterisation of products formed from the oxidation of guaiacol²¹, and other monohydric, dihydric, trihydric and polynuclear phenols²².

Amines :

Primary aromatic amines have been oxidised by various oxidants²³⁻²⁶, the major product obtained being azobenzene. The oxidative coupling of amines has been effected by KMnO_4 ²⁷, whereby *N*-phenyl-2-naphthylamine was converted to the 1,1-coupling dimer, and *N*-2-naphthyl-2-naphthylamine gave the corresponding carbon-carbon and carbon-nitrogen coupled products.

In the present investigation, the oxidative coupling of aniline and substituted aniline was brought about by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous

methanol solvent (Table 2). This Hammett plot gave a value of $\rho^+ = -1.0$ (corr. coeff. = 0.99), which

TABLE 2—RATE DATA FOR OXIDATION OF ANILINE AT 35.0°

[Aniline] $\times 10^3 M$	$[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$[NaOH]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_{obs} $\times 10^3 s^{-1}$
1.0	1.0	2.5	1.9
5.0	1.0	2.5	9.6
10.0	1.0	2.5	19.5
25.0	1.0	2.5	48.8
1.0	0.1	2.5	1.9
1.0	0.5	2.5	1.8
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.9
1.0	1.0	10.0	1.8
1.0	1.0	25.0	1.8
1.0	1.0	2.5	8.1 ^a
1.0	1.0	2.5	4.1 ^b
1.0	1.0	2.5	6.4 ^c

Aqueous methanol = 30% (v/v), $\mu = 0.1 M$. ^a45.0°; ^b50.0°; ^c60.0°; all temp. corrections were $\pm 0.1^\circ$; all values of rate constants were the average of two or more experiments, agreement being $\pm 3\%$.

was consistent with the formation of a radical intermediate in the rate-determining step of the reaction⁴. The esr spectrum of the radical generated from the oxidation of aniline, contained 4 sets of 1 : 2 : 1 triplets. This splitting pattern was attributed to the interaction of the unpaired electron spin with (i)

the nitrogen atom, (ii) the hydrogen atom attached to the nitrogen, and (iii) the two hydrogen atoms at positions *ortho* to the nitrogen atom. This spectrum was similar to that of the short-lived anilino radical (C_6H_5NH), observed during the flash photolysis of aniline in the gas phase²⁸ or by continuous irradiation in rigid glasses²⁹.

The mechanism for the oxidation of aniline by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) involved the formation of the radical intermediate, which underwent oxidative coupling to give the product azobenzene³⁰. The reaction sequence for this oxidation is

Oxidation of aromatic amines

The aromatic amines chosen for oxidation have included benzylamine and diphenylamine. On oxidation, diphenylamine yields different products, depending upon the oxidant and the conditions employed^{31,32}.

The rates of oxidation (of benzylamine and diphenylamine) by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous methanol solvent at constant ionic strength, were dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of both substrate and oxidant, but were independent of the concentration of alkali in the range studied. The Hammett plots of $\log k_{obs}$ against σ gave values of $\rho = -1.0$, indicating that the rate determining step involved the formation of a radical intermediate. The oxidation of benzylamine-*d*₂ exhibited a kinetic isotope effect with $k_H/k_D = 6.3$, indicating a cleavage of the C-H bond of the methylene group attached to the aryl ring, resulting in the formation of a radical intermediate.

The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of benzylamine, contained four sets of 1 : 2 : 1 triplets. This splitting pattern was attributed to the interaction of the unpaired electron spin with the nitrogen atom, with the hydrogen atom attached to the carbon atom and with the two hydrogen atoms at *ortho* positions in the aryl ring. The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of diphenylamine, gave a 1 : 2 : 1 triplet corresponding to a diphenylamino radical (Ar_2N). The coupling constants (in gauss) for the diphenylamino radical were $a_N = 8.85$, a_H (*ortho*) = 3.68, a_H (*meta*) = 1.50, a_H (*para*) = 4.30, with a value of $g_{av} = 2.0030 \pm 0.0002$.

The oxidation of diphenylamine resulted in the formation of tetraphenylhydrazine³⁸, thus

The oxidation of benzylamine gave benzaldehyde and ammonia³⁴, thus

Oxidation of N-alkyl side chains of amines

The oxidation of amines can be considered to occur either by a one-electron process, or by a two-electron process. In particular, amine oxide or hydroxylamine formation has been taken as evidence of two-electron transfer pathways in amine oxidations by H_2O_2 ³⁵, peroxyacids³⁶ and ozone³⁷. Amine oxides and alkyl cleavage products were predominant for the ozonation of aliphatic amines³⁷⁻³⁹. An amine oxide appears to be a crucial link in the biogenetic interrelationships of many alkaloids^{38,39}. The point of oxidation of the vast majority of alkaloids is the carbon atom that is either bonded to a nitrogen or can be placed in close proximity to it. The rearrangement of an amine oxide to a carbinolamine is not an uncommon phenomenon, the Polonovski rearrangement⁴⁰ being an example of such a transformation.

The mechanism by which a one-electron oxidising reagent reacts with amines in general, has been a subject of continuing interest. The one-electron oxidation reactions of amines were attributed to hydrogen atom transfer which directly gave a neutral radical intermediate capable of undergoing further oxidation⁴¹⁻⁴⁴, or of coupling^{45,46}.

The susceptibility of an amine to oxidation can be attributed to the availability of the unshared pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom. Generally, the first step in the oxidation of an amine involves the transfer of one or both of the electrons to the oxidant, followed by elimination of a proton to give a carbon radical or a carbonium ion. In some cases, the removal of the α -hydrogen is the initial step. Assuming that the oxidation is a one-step process, the two key steps can be depicted in the following manner⁴⁴,

In principle, the oxidation of an amine to an amide, parallels the oxidation of a primary alcohol to a carboxylic acid, thus

However, in practice, a variety of products may be obtained depending on the structure of the amine. When the amine is a primary amine and has a pair of α -hydrogen atoms, it is generally oxidised to a carboxylic acid with the elimination of ammonia. The reaction can be envisaged as proceeding through a carbinolamine that undergoes carbon-nitrogen bond cleavage, much more rapidly than oxidation, to give an amide. The aldehyde that is formed from the scission of the C-N bond is oxidised further to the acid.

The present study reports the kinetic features of the oxidation of amines wherein the oxidation occurs at the N-alkyl side chains, when the oxidation reactions were carried out using alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), at constant ionic strength, under nitrogen. The substrates have included aliphatic and aromatic amines.

Aliphatic amines (methylamine, dimethylamine, trimethylamine) :

The rates of these reactions were dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of substrate and oxidant, but were independent of the concentration of alkali in the range studied. Variations in the ionic strength of the medium, and the addition of hexacyanoferrate(II) ions did not have any effect on the rates. The esr spectra of the radicals, generated from the oxidation of both, methylamine and dimethylamine, gave 3 spectral lines with peak heights of 1:2:1. The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of trimethylamine, gave 9 spectral lines. The unpaired electron is subject to a strong interaction with the nitrogen atom ($I=1$, $a_N=10$ gauss) and weaker interactions with two magnetically equivalent protons ($I=1/2$, $a_H=1.5$ gauss). The spectrum observed consists of 3 main lines of equal intensity, 10 gauss apart, each of which is further split into a 1:2:1 triplet, the lines of which are separated by 1.5 gauss.

The mechanistic pathway for these reactions could be envisaged as proceeding via the removal

of the alpha hydrogen in the initial step, giving a radical intermediate. The subsequent steps were rapid, and no intermediate products could be isolated from the reaction mixture. Efforts to isolate the respective carbinolamines were not successful. It could be postulated that the carbinolamines when formed as intermediates, would be rapidly converted to the *N*-acyl derivatives. The oxidation of these aliphatic amines (methylamine to formamide, dimethylamine to formylmethylamine, and trimethylamine to formyldimethylamine) constitute examples of reactions wherein the oxidation occurs at the *N*-alkyl side chains, leading to the formation of *N*-aldehydes. Such products have been isolated and characterised in the MnO_2 oxidation of amines⁴³. The kinetic features of the oxidation of these aliphatic amines (methylamine, dimethylamine and trimethylamine) by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), have been reported in our earlier communications⁴⁷.

Aromatic amines (N-methylaniline, N-ethylaniline, N,N-dimethylaniline, N,N-diethylaniline) :

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) can bring about the oxidation of anilines with *N*-alkyl side chains. The rates of these reactions were dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of both substrate and oxidant, but were independent of the concentration of alkali, in the range studied. The addition of hexacyanoferrate(II) ions did not have any effect on the rates of these reactions, indicating that the first step of the reaction between the substrate and the oxidant (the electron abstraction step) was an irreversible step. An intermediate free radical was produced by the transfer of one electron, from the nitrogen atom of the amine to the oxidant. The intermediate species was postulated to be an aminium radical cation. Several examples of stable aminium radical cations have been reported⁴⁸⁻⁵². In the present investigation, evidence for the formation of radical intermediates was seen from the esr spectra. The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of *N,N*-dimethylaniline, gave 3 spectral lines with peak heights of 1 : 2 : 1. The esr spectrum of the radical, generated from the oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline, gave 12 spectral lines. The spectrum indicates that the 3 protons of the methyl group interact with the unpaired electron spin to give a hyperfine splitting of 27.0 gauss. The two methylene protons were magnetically equivalent with a splitting of 22.5 gauss.

The mechanistic pathway is supported by the observation of second order overall kinetics. An intermediate aminium radical cation was formed. The hydrogen abstraction reactions, leading to intermediate radical species, are two-step reactions. First, the electron is abstracted (rate limiting) and then the proton is removed by OH^- ion (fast step). This is the function of the required, but kinetically invisible base. This mechanism has been demonstrated for a related system⁵³. The subsequent steps were rapid, and the carbinolamine formed was rapidly converted to the *N*-acyl derivative.

In the oxidation of *N*-ethylaniline, the fast steps involved the elimination of water from the carbinolamine, and further oxidation of the resultant enamine gave the *N*-acyl derivative. The oxidation of the enamine most likely involved hydroxylation of the double bond followed by oxidative cleavage of the resultant α -glycol to yield the products. The oxidative cleavage of 1,2-glycols to yield the aldehydes has been established previously^{11,12}. In the oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline, the first step involved the oxidation to the carbinolamine which then underwent rearrangement, rapidly, to give the secondary amine (*N*-ethylaniline) and acetaldehyde. The secondary amine was then oxidised to formanilide and formaldehyde.

The oxidation of *N*-methylaniline, *N*-ethylaniline and *N,N*-diethylaniline to yield formanilide, and the oxidation of *N,N*-dimethylaniline to yield *N*-methylformanilide, constitute examples of reactions wherein the oxidation occurred at the *N*-alkyl side chains, leading to the formation of *N*-aldehydes⁵⁴. The sequence of reactions is shown in Schemes 3-4.

Scheme 3.

Scheme 4.

A significant observation was that while the oxidation of *N,N*-dimethylaniline by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) gave *N*-methylformanilide,

the alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline did not give any of the analogous *N*-ethylacetanilide, that is

Instead, the oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline gave formanilide and acetaldehyde, that is

Evidently, in the oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), the type of conversion (a) was totally excluded,

Instead, the type of conversion which dominated in the initial step was conversion (b),

In the later stage, the type of conversion was (c)

In an analogous oxidation of *N*-ethyl-*N*-methylaniline (3) by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), it was observed that a mixture of *N*-ethylformanilide (4) and formanilide (6) was obtained, that is

The formation of *N*-ethylformanilide (4) was an example of the type (a) conversion, while the formation of formanilide (6) represented the type (b) conversion.

Both *N*-methylaniline and *N*-ethylaniline were oxidised by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) to formanilide. However, the formanilide obtained from the oxidation of *N*-ethyl-*N*-methylaniline (3) probably involved the intermediacy of *N*-methylaniline (5) rather than *N*-ethylaniline. This transformation involved the cleavage of the C-H bond of the α -carbon of the ethyl group. This would be consistent with the fact that a secondary C-H bond was more reactive than a primary C-H bond.

Oxidative dealkylation of aliphatic amines

The oxidation of an α -carbon atom of an aliphatic tertiary amine followed by the cleavage of the C-N bond, has been observed in reactions between several oxidants and a variety of tertiary amines⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸. Such reactions are far more usual than amine oxide formation which is brought about only by H_2O_2 , peroxy acids, and under certain conditions, by ozone⁵⁹. Oxidative dealkylation also occurs in living organisms, and is a major pathway in the metabolism of certain drugs; it has been shown to be effected by the microsomal fraction of mammalian liver⁶⁰. Oxidation at the α -carbon is also involved in alkaloid biogenesis, as for example, the berberine bridge-carbon atom is derived from an *N*-methyl group⁶¹.

The present investigation reports the kinetic aspects of the oxidation of ethylamines (ethylamine, diethylamine and triethylamine) by aqueous hexacyanoferrate(III), under a nitrogen atmosphere, to give the products of oxidative dealkylation. The rate of the reaction was observed to be dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of substrate and oxidant. Oxidative dealkylation is typically seen in the reactions of hexacyanoferrate(III) with tertiary and secondary non-aromatic amines. The reactivity is in the order: $\text{R}_3\text{N} > \text{R}_2\text{NH} > \text{RNH}_2$, with RNH_2 relatively unreactive.

An analysis of the esr spectrum, obtained from the oxidation of triethylamine, showed that the paramagnetic species, stable at the reaction temperature, was $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\dot{\text{N}}^+$. The spectrum was resolved into 3 groups of lines with each group having equal intensity. This triplet was explained by the interaction of the unpaired electron in the radical with a nucleus of spin 1, presumably nitrogen. A total of 16 lines was observed within each group, of which the centre two lines were of equal intensity, indicating an interaction with an odd number of protons. A species, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\dot{\text{N}}^+$, with 15 protons, was thus inferred. The radical obtained from the oxidation of diethylamine was $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\dot{\text{N}}\text{H}^+$, which gave a 12-line spectrum. The isotropic coupling constants were 18.6 G for the

relating the rate of oxygen uptake by solutions of cysteine, glutathione and thioglycolic acid have been carried out.

In the present investigation, the kinetics of oxidation of some organic sulphur compounds (thiomalic acid, thioglycolic acid and thiophenol) by acidic hexacyanoferrate(III), showed a first order dependence on the concentrations of each – substrate and oxidant. The rates of the reactions showed a first order dependence on the concentration of acid (for thioglycolic acid and thiophenol), but showed an inverse dependence on the concentration of acid (for thiomalic acid). This inverse dependence on $[H^+]$ can be explained if the dissociation step of the sulphhydryl group in the thiol molecule is also included. This, however, appears unlikely in the acidic medium under consideration. In fact, it is difficult to state, with any certainty, the extent of involvement of protons vis-a-vis $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ and $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ ions. Ferricyanic acid is a strong acid, but ferrocyanic acid is strong only for the first two protons. The protonation of $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ would result in species such as $HFe(CN)_6^{2-}$, while the protonation of $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ would result in species such as $HFe(CN)_6^{3-}$ or $H_2Fe(CN)_6^{2-}$. These kinds of protonated species have been shown to be formed in acidic media^{7,8}.

The oxidation of thiomalic acid and thioglycolic acid had resulted in the formation of the thiyl radical intermediate, which showed a 1 : 2 : 1 triplet signal. The oxidation of thiophenol gave a radical intermediate which showed a 1 : 2 : 1 triplet signal, with a value of $g_{av} = 2.027 \pm 0.002$, indicating the presence of the thiophenyl radical ($C_6H_5S\cdot$). Oxidations producing radical intermediates are well-known in sulphur systems. The greater stability of these sulphur-containing radicals has been demonstrated by the experimental observation that α -mercapto acids yield disulphide as the reaction products. It could be suggested that disulphide was formed within the coordination sphere of the metal, or in a step concerted with the release of the thiyl radical. As in the case of cyanide complexes, it can be assumed that the oxidation of thiols occurred by an outer sphere process, and hence thiyl radicals were formed which would undergo rapid dimerisation to yield the disulphide.

In the oxidation of thiomalic acid, it can be assumed that the thiol exists mostly in the ionised form in aqueous medium. Owing to the acidic medium employed, this would preclude the ionisation of the weak sulphhydryl group. Since disulphide was the final product of oxidation, the sulphhydryl group (SH) provides the site of attack. If the species, CH_2COO^- , is designated as HSR^{2-} then

the proposed mechanism can be written as

For the oxidation of thioglycolic acid in acid medium, ionised species would be present, according to the equilibrium,

If the reactive species, $^-SCH_2COO^-$ is designated as RS^{2-} , then the proposed mechanism can be represented as^{9,10}

It has been suggested that since the dissociation of the lowest triplet excited states of thiophenol was not possible, the breakdown occurred from the lowest excited singlet state following charge neutralisation of the parent ion, with S-H cleavage being the only important process¹¹. The radiolysis of thiophenol gave an appreciable yield of hydrogen, indicating the dominant role that the sulphhydryl group exerts when it is present in a molecule. The significant process becomes that of hydrogen abstraction from sulphur, resulting in the formation of the thiophenyl radical. The oxidation of thiophenol can be represented as¹²

Inorganic sulphur compounds :

The mechanism by which a one-electron oxidising agent such as potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) reacts with two-electron reducing agents such as sulphite and thiosulphate, is a subject of current interest. One-electron transfer agents convert sulphite to dithionate, $S_2O_8^{2-}$ (via the radical anion, $SO_3^{\cdot-}$), whereas two-electron oxidants tend to produce sulphate.

The present work is a kinetic investigation of the oxidation of sulphite and thiosulphate by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) at constant ionic strength.

The reaction between sulphite and hexacyanoferrate(III) was observed to be dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of each – substrate, oxidant and alkali. The reaction between thiosulphate hexacyanoferrate(III) was dependent on the first powers of the concentrations of substrate and oxidant, but was independent of the concentration of alkali.

The redox potentials for the $SO_3^{2-} / S_2O_8^{2-}$ and $Fe(CN)_6^{3-} / Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ couples were thermodynamically favourable for electron transfer between substrate and oxidant. It can be postulated that the mechanistic pathway involved a direct interaction between the reactants. When the experiment

was conducted in the presence of $^{14}\text{CN}^-$, there was no labeled cyano ligand in the $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ product, ensuring the absence of cyano exchange.

The presence of SO_3^- radical in reactions involving the oxidation of SO_3^{2-} , and the inhibitive action of alcohols on such reactions has been suggested⁸³. Evidence has been presented to suggest that a radical mechanism is important in the oxidation of sulphite⁸⁴.

The addition of a free radical inhibitor, mannitol, had no effect on the observed rate of oxidation of thiosulphate, suggesting that the involvement of free radicals in the rate-determining step of the reaction was unlikely⁸⁴. The reaction between thiosulphate and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ occurred by a one-equivalent electron transfer, giving rise to a singly charged anion (S_2O_3^-). The rapid dimerisation of S_2O_3^- gave tetrathionate ions, $\text{S}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$. The sequence of reactions can be represented as follows⁸⁴ :

(a) Oxidation of sulphite :

(b) Oxidation of thiosulphate :

Conclusions :

This paper has attempted to highlight the kinetic features of the oxidation of various kinds of organic and inorganic substrate by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), and to suggest mechanistic pathways, in order to bring out the efficiency of this oxidising agent in effecting diverse kinds of transformations. This study also demonstrates the usefulness of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) as a reagent with wide synthetic utility.

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